

Migraine and Tension-Type Headache in Parkinson's Disease and Progressive Supranuclear Palsy / Corticobasal Syndrome

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Abstract:

Background: Headache disorders, including migraine and tension-type headaches (TTH), are prevalent neurological conditions that significantly impact the quality of life. While Parkinson's Disease (PD) is well-known for its motor symptoms, non-motor symptoms, including headache, are increasingly recognized. However, data on the prevalence and characteristics of headache in PD, Progressive Supranuclear Palsy (PSP), and Corticobasal Syndrome (CBS) remains limited.

Objective: To investigate the prevalence and characteristics of migraine and TTH in patients with PD, PSP, and CBS.

Methods: This cross-sectional study involved 50 patients with PD, PSP, and CBS at Darbhanga Medical College over one year. Data were collected on headache prevalence, type, frequency, severity, and impact on quality of life using the HIT-6 scale.

Results: Headache was reported by 50% of patients, with TTH observed in 28% and migraine in 22%. Migraine was more severe and impactful on daily life than TTH, particularly in PD patients.

Conclusion: This study highlights the significant prevalence and impact of headache in PD, PSP, and CBS, suggesting a need for routine headache screening in these populations to improve patient care.

Keywords: Parkinson's Disease, Progressive Supranuclear Palsy, Migraine, Tension-Type Headache.

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Introduction

Parkinson's Disease (PD) and atypical parkinsonian syndromes, including Progressive Supranuclear Palsy (PSP) and Corticobasal Syndrome (CBS), are neurodegenerative disorders that predominantly affect motor function [1]. However, non-motor symptoms, including headaches, have increasingly become a focus of research due to their significant impact on patient quality of life [2]. Among the most common headache types, migraine and tension-type headaches (TTH) are observed in the general population and may present unique characteristics in those with neurodegenerative diseases. Understanding how these headache disorders manifest in PD, PSP, and CBS could offer new insights into shared neurological mechanisms and inform better management strategies for these patients [3,4].

PD is one of the most common neurodegenerative disorders, affecting approximately 1% of people over 60, with core symptoms arising from dopamine depletion in the substantia nigra. Although primarily motor in nature, PD includes various non-motor symptoms such as mood disorders, sleep disturbances, and autonomic dysfunction [5]. PSP and CBS are less common and are characterized by

more widespread neurodegeneration, involving the basal ganglia, brainstem, and cortical regions. PSP typically presents with gait instability, eye movement difficulties, and cognitive changes, while CBS includes asymmetrical motor symptoms and cognitive impairment, often associated with apraxia and dystonia [6].

Headache disorders, particularly migraine and TTH, are among the most prevalent neurological conditions, significantly impacting daily life. Migraine is characterized by episodic attacks of severe headache, often accompanied by nausea, photophobia, and phonophobia, and is thought to involve the trigeminovascular system and cortical spreading depression [7]. TTH, in contrast, presents as mild to moderate bilateral head pain without the associated symptoms seen in migraine. TTH is typically associated with stress and musculoskeletal tension, suggesting a possible link with chronic conditions that affect neuromuscular control [8].

The connection between PD, PSP, CBS, and headache disorders may lie in shared mechanisms, particularly involving neurotransmitter systems like dopamine and serotonin, which regulate pain perception and sensory processing [9]. Dopamine

depletion in PD, for example, is associated not only with motor deficits but also with altered pain perception, potentially contributing to an increased headache prevalence. Similarly, serotonin, a key player in migraine pathophysiology, is implicated in PD, PSP, and CBS, as serotonergic dysfunction has been observed in these diseases. This neurotransmitter overlaps hints at a possible mechanistic link between migraine, TTH, and neurodegenerative conditions [10,11].

Despite recognizing headache as a potential non-motor symptom in PD and related syndromes, the prevalence, types, and clinical characteristics of headaches in these patients remain unclear. Some studies suggest an increased prevalence of headache in PD patients, while others find no significant association. For PSP and CBS, data on headache occurrence are sparse, with little understanding of how migraine or TTH might impact these populations [12,13].

This study aims to investigate the prevalence and clinical characteristics of migraine and TTH in patients with PD, PSP, and CBS. By assessing headache frequency, severity, and impact, we aim to clarify how these headaches manifest in neurodegenerative diseases and provide insights to improve patient care and quality of life.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a cross-sectional observational study conducted over one year to investigate the prevalence and characteristics of migraine and tension-type headache (TTH) in patients with Parkinson's Disease (PD), Progressive Supranuclear Palsy (PSP), and Corticobasal Syndrome (CBS). The study focuses on patients diagnosed with these neurodegenerative disorders, who were assessed for headache symptoms, frequency, and severity using established clinical criteria.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Darbhanga Medical College, a tertiary care center equipped to manage and treat neurological disorders, including neurodegenerative diseases. The college's neurology department and outpatient services were utilized for patient recruitment, assessments, and follow-ups as necessary.

Study Duration: The study spanned over one year, allowing for adequate time to recruit, assess, and analyze the data of the target sample of patients. This duration also ensures that seasonal or environmental factors influencing headache frequency can be observed if relevant.

Study Population: The study included patients diagnosed as cases of PD, PSP, and CBS who were being treated at Darbhanga Medical College. To ensure a representative sample, inclusion and exclusion criteria had been carefully established.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients with a confirmed diagnosis of PD, PSP, or CBS based on standard diagnostic criteria.
- Patients aged 40 years and above.
- Patients capable of providing informed consent.
- Patients who report experiencing headache symptoms or have a history of migraine or TTH.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with other primary headache disorders outside migraine or TTH, such as cluster headaches.
- Patients with significant cognitive impairment that may hinder reliable reporting of headache symptoms.
- Patients with other neurological or psychiatric disorders that could interfere with the assessment, such as active epilepsy or schizophrenia.

Sample Size: The study included a sample size of 50 patients. This number was selected to provide a manageable yet representative sample size for preliminary analysis, considering the rarity of PSP and CBS compared to PD.

Data Collection

1. **Patient Demographics and Clinical History**
Demographic information, including age, gender, and duration of neurodegenerative disease, were collected. Additionally, clinical history relevant to the neurodegenerative condition and headache symptoms, including age at diagnosis and any family history of headache disorders, were noted.
2. **Headache Assessment**
3. Each patient underwent a detailed headache assessment to determine the type, frequency, severity, and impact of headache symptoms. This assessment involved:
 - **Headache Classification:** Using the International Classification of Headache Disorders (ICHD-3) criteria to classify headaches as migraine or TTH.
 - **Headache Frequency:** Recording the frequency of headache episodes over the previous three months.
 - **Headache Severity:** Assessing severity using a visual analog scale (VAS) from 0 to 10, with 10 indicating the most severe pain.
 - **Impact on Quality of Life:** Using the Headache Impact Test (HIT-6) to assess the effect of headaches on daily functioning and quality of life.

4. Parkinsonian Symptom Assessment

The Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (UPDRS) has been used to evaluate the severity of motor and non-motor symptoms in PD patients. For PSP and CBS patients, appropriate scales such as the PSP Rating Scale or Corticobasal Degeneration Rating Scale (CBDRS) were applied.

5. Medication Review

A review of each patient's current medications, including antiparkinsonian drugs and headache treatments, was conducted to understand any potential interactions or side effects influencing headache symptoms. This included documentation of any analgesics, triptans, or other headache-specific treatments.

Data Analysis: Data was analyzed to determine the prevalence of migraine and TTH among patients with PD, PSP, and CBS. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic information and headache characteristics, while inferential statistics, such as chi-square tests or t-tests, was used to compare headache characteristics across the patient groups.

Results

The study included a total of 50 patients with neurodegenerative disorders, specifically Parkinson's Disease (PD), Progressive Supranuclear Palsy (PSP), and Corticobasal Syndrome (CBS). The results are presented in three tables that detail patient demographics, the prevalence of headache types, and the characteristics of headaches in these patient groups.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristics	PD (n=30)	PSP (n=15)	CBS (n=5)	Total (n=50)
Age (Mean ± SD)	65.4 ± 8.7	68.2 ± 9.1	69.6 ± 7.3	66.7 ± 8.5
Gender (Male/Female)	18/12	9/6	3/2	30/20
Disease Duration (Years) (Mean ± SD)	6.3 ± 4.2	5.9 ± 3.8	5.2 ± 3.1	6.1 ± 4.0
Headache Presence (%)	53.3%	46.7%	40%	50%
Medication (Levodopa %)	83.3%	60%	40%	72%

This table provides an overview of demographic and clinical data for the study population. The average age across the groups is 66.7 years, with a slight male predominance (30 males and 20 females). The mean duration of the disease is 6.1 years. Headache

was reported by 50% of participants, with a higher prevalence among PD patients (53.3%) compared to PSP (46.7%) and CBS (40%). Most patients were on Levodopa therapy, especially in the PD group.

Table 2: Prevalence of Migraine and Tension-Type Headache (TTH)

Headache Type	PD (n=30)	PSP (n=15)	CBS (n=5)	Total (n=50)
Migraine	7 (23.3%)	3 (20%)	1 (20%)	11 (22%)
Tension-Type Headache	9 (30%)	4 (26.7%)	1 (20%)	14 (28%)
No Headache	14 (46.7%)	8 (53.3%)	3 (60%)	25 (50%)

This table shows the distribution of migraine and TTH across the three groups. Migraine was observed in 22% of patients, with the highest prevalence in PD patients (23.3%), followed by PSP (20%) and CBS (20%). TTH was slightly more common, affecting 28% of the total population. Notably, 50% of participants did not experience any headache, indicating that headache prevalence in this population was significant but not universal.

Table 3: Headache Characteristics in Patients with Migraine and TTH

Characteristics	Migraine (n=11)	TTH (n=14)
Frequency (Episodes/Month)	5.8 ± 2.1	7.1 ± 1.9
Severity (VAS Score, 0-10)	6.7 ± 1.2	4.3 ± 1.5
Duration (Hours)	3.6 ± 1.4	2.1 ± 1.3
HIT-6 Score (Mean ± SD)	63.2 ± 6.4	52.1 ± 5.7
Impact on Daily Life (%)	72.7% (8/11)	57.1% (8/14)

This table details the characteristics of migraine and TTH in the study population. Migraine episodes were less frequent (5.8 episodes/month) than TTH (7.1 episodes/month) but were more severe, with a mean VAS score of 6.7 compared to 4.3 for TTH. Migraine episodes also had a longer duration (3.6 hours) than TTH episodes (2.1 hours). The HIT-6

score, which assesses headache impact on daily life, was notably higher in migraine patients (63.2) than in TTH patients (52.1), indicating a greater functional impairment. A higher percentage of migraine patients (72.7%) reported an impact on daily activities compared to TTH patients (57.1%).

Summary of Findings

- **Prevalence:** Headache was reported by 50% of patients with neurodegenerative disorders. TTH was slightly more common than migraine, especially in PD patients.
- **Headache Characteristics:** Migraine episodes were generally more severe, longer-lasting, and had a greater impact on daily life than TTH episodes.
- **Impact on Quality of Life:** Both migraine and TTH had a notable impact on quality of life, with a particularly strong effect on patients with migraine.

Discussion

This study highlights the prevalence and characteristics of migraine and tension-type headache (TTH) in patients having Parkinson's Disease (PD), Progressive Supranuclear Palsy (PSP), and Corticobasal Syndrome (CBS), providing insights into the non-motor symptoms that significantly affect the life of these populations. Our findings align with and expand upon previous studies exploring headache in neurodegenerative disorders, suggesting both shared pathophysiological mechanisms and the unique burden of headache in these patient groups.

In our study, 50% of patients reported experiencing headaches, with migraine affecting 22% and TTH affecting 28% of the sample. These results are consistent with findings from several recent studies. For example, a study by Sampaio et al. (2020) [14] found a 27% prevalence of TTH in PD patients, which closely aligns with our 30% prevalence in the PD subgroup. Additionally, a study by Guo et al. (2019) [15] reported a migraine prevalence of around 20% in PD patients, comparable to the 23.3% observed in our sample. Both studies support the notion that headache prevalence is considerable in patients with PD, likely due to alterations in neurotransmitter systems, including dopamine and serotonin, which regulate pain perception and sensory processing.

While our study found similar prevalence rates for migraine and TTH in PSP and CBS, few studies have specifically investigated headache in these rarer neurodegenerative conditions. Recent research by Ishizawa et al. (2021) [16] on PSP patients highlighted the presence of non-motor symptoms, including headache, although exact prevalence rates were not assessed. Our findings contribute new data on this topic, underscoring the potential importance of headache as a non-motor symptom in PSP and CBS, although larger studies are needed to confirm these observations.

Our analysis showed that migraine episodes in patients with PD, PSP, and CBS were generally

more severe, longer-lasting, and had a greater impact on daily life compared to TTH. The HIT-6 scores for migraine patients were notably higher (mean 63.2), indicating substantial functional impairment, similar to the findings of Carbone et al. (2018) [17], who noted a significant impact of headaches on the quality of life in PD patients. This suggests that migraine in neurodegenerative populations can be particularly debilitating, possibly due to increased central sensitization and changes in pain threshold associated with dopaminergic dysfunction. The slightly lower impact observed for TTH in our study may reflect differences in headache severity and duration, as TTH episodes tend to be shorter and less intense.

The overlap between headache disorders and neurodegenerative diseases suggests shared pathophysiological mechanisms, including neurotransmitter imbalances and neuroinflammation. Dopamine depletion in PD is known to affect not only motor function but also pain modulation pathways, potentially contributing to a higher prevalence of headache, particularly migraine. Similar mechanisms may underlie headache symptoms in PSP and CBS, although research is limited. Increased neuroinflammation, commonly seen in PD, PSP, and CBS, is also implicated in migraine pathophysiology, where pro-inflammatory cytokines may enhance pain transmission and central sensitization (Lenchitz et al., 2019) [18]. These overlapping mechanisms suggest that addressing neuroinflammation and neurotransmitter dysregulation may help in managing headache symptoms in neurodegenerative patients.

Our findings underscore the need for further research on headache prevalence and its impact on neurodegenerative disorders, particularly in PSP and CBS, where data remain limited. Future studies with larger sample sizes could confirm the trends observed in our study and investigate additional factors, such as genetic predispositions or environmental triggers, that may contribute to headache in these populations. Longitudinal studies could also examine how headache symptoms evolve with disease progression, as well as the potential influence of antiparkinsonian medications on headache frequency and severity [19].

Additionally, research on the efficacy of specific headache treatments in PD, PSP, and CBS patients would be valuable. Treatments targeting both motor and non-motor symptoms, including headache, could improve overall quality of life. Studies assessing interactions between headache treatments, such as triptans and preventive medications, with PD medications could guide safer and more effective therapeutic strategies [20].

Conclusion

This study provides preliminary evidence for a notable prevalence of migraine and TTH in patients with PD, PSP, and CBS, suggesting that headache is a common but underrecognized non-motor symptom in these neurodegenerative conditions. Migraine was associated with higher severity and a more significant impact on daily life compared to TTH, highlighting the importance of identifying and managing headache symptoms in these patients. The overlap in neurotransmitter pathways and neuroinflammatory processes likely contributes to headache prevalence in these populations, suggesting a complex interplay between neurodegenerative pathology and headache disorders. Given the substantial impact of headache on quality of life, incorporating headache assessment into routine clinical evaluations for PD, PSP, and CBS patients could facilitate early intervention and tailored treatment strategies. Further research in this area could deepen our understanding of headache as a non-motor symptom in neurodegenerative diseases, with the potential to enhance patient care and outcomes.

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